

Cost-sensitive Decision Trees as Post-hoc Explanation Model in Model-Agnostic XAI method*

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Abstract

In recent years there is increasing demand for comprehension and explainability of the inferences machine learning models make. Many explainable artificial intelligence (xAI) methods have been introduced as a tool for better understanding of decision-making process of complex AI models. The doctoral research aims to develop a new model-agnostic xAI framework for classification tasks by using cost-sensitive decision trees and argumentation decision graphs. From the classification problem point of view, especially if a dataset is imbalanced, the cost-sensitive decision tree (CSDT) method can be used for generating an acceptably accurate ML model by taking imbalanced ratio into the consideration during the tree building procedure. On the other side, from the explainability perspective, generated cost-sensitive tree model can be more comprehensible compared to the tree model generated using traditional (cost-insensitive) decision tree learning algorithm, due to smaller tree size of the cost-sensitive tree. However, to have more plausibly accurate ML model for given imbalanced classification task, deep learning algorithms could be applied, leading to more complex, non-linear models whose decision-making process is hard to understand and explain. For such complex models, we can create interpretable surrogate model that will approximate the predictions of the underlying model as accurately as possible, while at the same time being interpretable and easy to explain. For the purpose of creating surrogate model, a cost-sensitive decision tree learning algorithm can be used. By having a CSDT model, it is possible to obtain explanation for any sample as a rule extracted from the tree. Thereby, we can consider cost-sensitive tree as a rule-extraction xAI method. Current research show that argumentation graph can represent the logic of the complex model with fewer rules than a decision tree. The aim of the study is to investigate possible ways of transforming cost-sensitive tree model into an argumentation decision graph in order to create a more concise structure that should be more understandable. The final step of generating argument-based explanations is evaluation by using both quantitative and human-center analysis.

Keywords

Explainable Artificial Intelligence, Model Agnostic Explanations, Explainable Surrogate Models, Cost-sensitive Decision Tree, Argumentation, Machine Learning

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1. Introduction and research motivation

Predictive machine learning models play a crucial role in various fields, from finance, agriculture, to healthcare. As the availability of data exponentially increases, machine learning (ML) methods, particularly deep learning methods, have led to the creation of powerful models. However, many of these models are characterized by complex, non-linear structures that can be challenging to interpret and explain. One of the important factors when using the ML model in production regardless of the domain of application, or in research, is the interpretability of the model [1]. Many explainable artificial intelligence (xAI) methods have been introduced as a tool for a better understanding of the inference process of complex ML models. Since there is a plethora of xAI methods, recently there have been many attempts to make a unified division of xAI methods [2, 3]. Some approaches in the categorization of the xAI methods focus on the type of input data used to train the ML model, others focus on the internal mechanisms of the xAI method, while some focus on the scope i.e. whether the xAI method generates local and/or global explanations. Another way to segregate the xAI method is by determining whether the method is post-hoc or ante-hoc (inherently transparent). The former methods enable an understanding of the black-box model a posteriori. The advantage of any post-hoc method is that there is no influence on the performance of the black box model which is important due to a trade-off between predictive performance and transparency, as the two objectives are conflicted [4]. This problem and many other challenges related to xAI are discussed in several papers [5, 6, 7].

The doctoral research aims to develop a new post-hoc, model-agnostic xAI framework for classification tasks by using cost-sensitive decision trees and argumentation decision graphs. Creating a new post-hoc, model-agnostic method is motivated by the fact that generating a posteriori explanation can be the only solution for explaining already trained black-box ML models. The method to be developed will be model agnostic, hence there will not exist requirements in terms of understanding the inner workings of the ML model to be explained. For any complex model, it can be created an interpretable surrogate model that will approximate the predictions of the underlying model as accurately as possible, while at the same time being interpretable and easy to explain. To create a surrogate model, a cost-sensitive decision tree (CSDT) learning algorithm can be used. By having a CSDT model, it is possible to obtain an explanation for any sample as a rule extracted from the tree. Thereby, we can consider a cost-sensitive tree as a rule-extraction xAI method. Although tree-based models are considered as naturally transparent and interpretable, for a layman it can be difficult to comprehend explanations given by the decision tree model, especially if the tree model is large. Current research [8] shows that an argumentation graph can represent the logic of a complex model with fewer rules than a decision tree. In our framework one of the objectives is to use CSDT model since generated CSDT model can be more comprehensible compared to the tree model generated using a traditional (cost-insensitive) decision tree learning algorithm, due to the smaller tree size of the cost-sensitive tree. The extracted rules from any tree-based model should mimic the inferential process of a complex ML model [4, 9]. To bridge the gap between lack of transparency and non-linearity of complex ML model, the aim of the doctoral research is to develop new xAI method that will be based on rules extracted from a surrogate CSDT model, further transforming the rules into an argumentation decision graph.

2. Key related works that frame the research

2.1. Surrogate xAI models

One of the most popular model-agnostic xAI approaches is creating surrogate model for the complex ML model to be explained. The surrogate model is created to accurately approximate the predictions of the complex, black-box ML model, while still being interpretable. The only requirement for the approach is to have training data and the predictions of the model to be explained. The surrogate model can be global or local, depending on the dataset used for training the model. The surrogate model is local if it is trained on a subset of the original data or weighted data.

According to the mentioned categories introduced in the introduction of this paper, the LIME method can be classified as a post-hoc model-agnostic explanation method. The method is local meaning it generates an explanation for a given sample. First is generated a new set of samples in the proximity the sample to be explained and then a local interpretable model is trained. In many research studies [10, 11, 12], as an interpretable model is used linear model. The LIME method has a problem with stability and local fidelity, meaning the model has problem with generating the same explanations for the same sample in several runs, and the learned explanation model should be a good local approximation of the model being explained. There are many studies that tried to improve the LIME and resolve these issues.

Some of the mentioned problems are tried to be resolved by the ALIME method ([11]) that uses autoencoders for assigning weights for samples. Unlike LIME that sample data randomly, the ALIME uses an autoencoder to weight new data around the sample. However, the ALIME also uses linear model as a local surrogate model. The results of the evaluating explanations provided by using local interpretable model ([13]) show that participants in the survey struggled to understand and interpret the feature scores and prediction probability since the feature scores do not add up to the prediction probability. Therefore, other interpretable models such as tree-based models could be used.

In [14] is proposed new approach, modified version of ALIME, which uses a decision tree as an interpretable model. They proposed tree-ALIME, autoencoder-based approach for local interpretability. As their results of evaluating tree-ALIME show, using a decision tree model as a local interpretable model is promising. However, the results show that using a decision tree model instead of a linear model, did not improve local fidelity. As explained, the main reason for such results is probably a simple decision tree model (maximal depth of the tree is set to be 5) and a tendency of tree models to overfit the data. More importantly, regarding interpretability, the decision tree model gained significantly better results compared to the linear model. Therefore, other tree-based algorithms can be used in the proposed approach to tackle all aforementioned challenges. In the abundance of tree-based models, one of the options is the cost-sensitive decision tree algorithm. Furthermore, any decision tree algorithm including cost-sensitive decision tree algorithm, can be used to create a global surrogate model.

2.2. Cost-sensitive decision tree

The cost-sensitive decision tree (CSDT) method [15] is a machine learning algorithm for generating a tree model by considering the cost matrix during the tree-building procedure. The

CSDT method belongs to the group of cost-sensitive learning methods ([16]), that can be used in the more narrow imbalanced learning framework. To use cost-sensitive learning methods for a two-class classification problem, where majority class samples occur more frequently, we can assume that samples from the minority class have higher cost(s). This approach can be seen as an algorithm-level solution for the class imbalance problem, since there is an adaptation of existing classification learning algorithms to improve performance with regards to the minority class, whereas data-level solutions assume different rebalancing techniques to make data distribution more balanced. Manipulating the data distribution has limits and costs associated with an attempt to make the distribution more balanced. Therefore, using algorithm-level solutions such as the CSDT model might be more convenient option. From the classification problem point of view, especially if a dataset is imbalanced, the cost-sensitive tree method can be used for generating an acceptably accurate ML model by considering the imbalanced ratio during the tree-building procedure. On the other hand, from the explainability perspective, a cost-sensitive tree model can be more comprehensible compared to the traditional decision tree learning algorithm.

The tree structure of the model enables us to create explanation for each sample by following the path from the root node to the leaf node of the decision tree determined by feature values of the sample. The path from the root node to a leaf node explains why the model classified the sample in the given class. To create a CSDT model it must be given the test set, the prediction labels of the corresponding test set obtained from the black box ML model to be explained, and the cost matrix. In general, a cost matrix can be either class-dependent (all samples from the same class have the same misclassification costs) or sample-dependent (each sample has its cost matrix defined). When the costs are unknown, the demand for cost-sensitive information represents difficulty in using a CSDT algorithm. To overcome this problem in an imbalance framework, one possible solution is to assume the class-dependent case and observe the costs as hyperparameters, and search for optimal cost values using some optimization technique. Furthermore, if the target variable has two classes, without loss of generality, we can impose a condition that the misclassification cost for false positives are equal to 1 and search only for the cost of false negatives. In other words, an arbitrary cost matrix can be normalized to become a cost matrix satisfying these conditions [17, 18]. Having proper cost-matrix defined is essential for cost-sensitive tree-building process, since the CSDT algorithm chooses a feature that reduces the misclassification cost the most. That is, the CSDT uses the cost-sensitive splitting criterion. Unlike traditional decision tree, a cost-sensitive tree will classify the sample in the region to the least costly class. The resulting product is the tree object, as in any other tree-based ML algorithm, that is considered naturally transparent and explainable. Nevertheless, any tree model can be hard to understand if the model is deep, and this might be the case if the cost-sensitive tree-model is used as a surrogate model. To be reliable, a CSDT surrogate model must achieve an accuracy score equal to one. That is, the surrogate model must be able to predict the same output as the complex ML model before providing explanations. Therefore, the generated tree model might be deep and hence it can be hard to comprehend its inference process. All things considered, the doctoral research broaden the scope into the argumentation framework.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the new post-hoc, model-agnostic xAI method.

2.3. Argumentation graph framework

Argumentation is a multidisciplinary subfield of AI that studies how arguments can be presented in a defeasible reasoning process and how to evaluate the validity of the conclusions reached at the end of the reasoning process [8]. Argument-based systems are typically built upon multi-layer schema. Argumentation has several important concepts: arguments, attacks and semantics [19]. The arguments are rules and attacks are binary relations between two conflicting rules (arguments). Three classes of conflicts can be distinguished [19]. A fundamental feature of argument based system is ability to determine the success of an attack [8]. For example to decide if an attack is valid the strengths of arguments or attacks can be used [19].

Argumentative decision graphs (ADGs) have a rule-based structure where each argument has a single premise and a conclusion. The well-formed ADG can be extracted from a decision tree, by taking each terminal node in the tree to generate a predictive argument in the ADG, while non terminal nodes could be used as non predictive arguments [20]. The attacks could be generated between arguments with different features and conclusions that are in disjoint paths and lead to distinct terminal nodes.

In the [20] is proposed new argumentation decision graph method where the emphasis was on decision trees and argumentative models. They showed that based on tree model, proposed method could create extended argumentative decision graph of equivalent inferential capability that could be perceived as more understandable. It is important that derived argumentative model is guaranteed to maintain the same inferential capability, still being smaller in terms of a size. They analysed whether reasonably smaller structures, in terms of number of arguments/attacks and amount of argument supports, can be achieved for classification tasks.

3. Specific research questions, hypothesis and objectives

The doctoral research will be carried out in a several phases described in the following paragraphs and depicted in the diagram (Figure 1).

Having the dataset spitted onto the train and test subset, the black-box ML model is trained on the train subset and evaluated on the test. Next step is to provide understanding into the inference process of the the complex ML model which will be done in phases. First phase is

creating a surrogate model, that can be done either locally or globally, by using inherently interpretable tree model i.e. cost-sensitive decision tree. Choosing the appropriate approach to create a surrogate cost-sensitive tree model is one important step in our methodology. Therefore the research question we aim to answer in the first phase is: what is most appropriate approach to create surrogate model by using CSDT?

The second phase has an objective to transform obtained rules from CSDT into explainable argument-based representation. The process can be broken down into five layers [19]: 1. definition of the internal structure of arguments 2. definition of conflicts between arguments 3. evaluation of conflicts and definition of valid attacks 4. definition of the dialectical status of arguments 5. accrual of acceptable arguments. One of our research questions related to argumentation is: whether the weighted notion of argument or attack should be considered in our framework, where weights would represent the strength of the argument or attack measured by considering misclassification cost reduction? For example, if two paths in the tree model are conflicted, weights could be computed as the misclassification cost of samples belonging to the intersection of the covers of two conflicting rules that are assigned by the model to the same target class of the conclusion of the attacking rule.

Given a set of arguments with defined attacks, a further decision that must be made is which arguments can be accepted. Different semantics can be used, leading to a set of arguments with a status (rank). In [?, lucas]s shown that rules from a tree model exploited by an extension based semantics, such as grounded, results in ADG with the same set of inferences as the tree. Therefore, another question is related to the choice of semantics designed for handling the weighted argumentation framework.

The extend argumentative decision graph (xADG) is proposed in [20] as new framework that allows for arguments to use boolean logic operators and multiple premises within their internal structure, resulting in more concise argumentation graphs that may be easier for users to understand. The xADG of equivalent inferential capability as ADG, is formed by performing a set of modifications. We aim to test if the proposed framework xADG can be applied to ADG built from CSDT and what modifications are needed if weighted argumentation is going to be used.

4. Current results and next steps

To date, the CSDT models are trained on various datasets with different class imbalance ratios. The current results show that cost-sensitive tree model is less complex compared to the traditional decision-tree model, for the same tree depth, without pruning procedure. In further work, we aim to extend the number of datasets used for the comparison purposes in order to test if rules extracted from a cost-sensitive decision tree model are consistently shorter than the rules extracted from the decision tree model.

The next step, a CSDT will be created as global or local surrogate model for some complex ML model such as deep neural network model. However, in local explanation framework, the influence of all features and their importance is calculated on a local level, hence for each test sample it will be generated one CSDT model and lead to forest of CSDT models. One of the local approaches is to use autoencoder-based modification as is done in [11] and test if there are

improvements in terms of local fidelity and stability. Another option is to create global CSDT surrogate model. Afterwards, the CSDT should be transformed into argumentation decision graph to generate simpler rules that are potentially more comprehensible as is done in [20].

The final step of generating argument-based explanations will be evaluation. In general, two ways of evaluating interpretability of the model can be distinguished: quantitative and human-centered evaluations. The latter can include domain experts and/or people unfamiliar with concepts such as ML and xAI, in order to evaluate obtained explanations provided to individuals with diverse knowledge. As is done in the study [8], we can select several metrics to quantitatively assess the degree of explainability of the rules extracted from the CSDT and the rules of argumentation-based graph. For human-centred evaluation purposes of explanations produced, in future work the human-centred psychometric test [21] could be used. Developed argument-based model-agnostic xAI method should also be compared to other rule-based xAI methods [8, 20].

5. Final contribution

The end product of the doctoral research is model-agnostic argument-based xAI method developed by extraction of rules and their conflicts from CSDT models and their integration into an argumentation framework that can serve as a mechanism for interpreting and explaining the inferential process of complex ML models.

Leveraging the structure and inferential capability of CSDT with argumentation decision graph could be promising direction in automating the creation of structured argumentation frameworks with reasonable size that will be more easy to comprehend.

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